

Supplementary materials

Dynamic parental roles revealed by fine-scale hunting behaviour with concurrent pair tracking in the wild

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Biparentality proportion related to specific landscape features

All variables including “_z” or “.z” are continuous variables standardised as z-scores. If they include “log” or “sqrt” means that they have been log- or sqrt-transformed. These variables are listed and explained in the Methods sub-section “Environmental variables” of the main text.

Figure S1. Univariate model coefficients of habitat feature predictors related to biparentality proportion. Models are ordered by the best predictive to the worst, reflecting the model selection reported in Table S1 below.

Model comparisons:			
	elpd_diff	se_diff	variable
modelIDenv1	0.0	0.0	wildflower area
modelIDenv3	-26.0	141.1	distance to forest
modelIDenv8	-33.8	129.4	distance to city/settlement
modelIDenv11	-63.7	109.7	crop diversity
modelIDenv10	-66.0	107.8	meadow area
modelIDenv6	-66.0	97.0	grassland area
modelIDenv7	-70.6	90.5	hedgerow area
modelIDenv5	-74.5	101.9	city/settlement area
modelIDenv9	-78.5	96.2	extensive pasture area
modelIDenv2	-78.7	94.8	distance to road
modelIDenv4	-84.5	107.1	distance to city/settlement

Table S1. Model comparison between univariate models predicting relationship between pair biparentality proportion and habitat features, to justify the use of wildflower strips area in our Bayesian GLMM reported in our models in the main texts.

Biparental care and brood size

Figure S2. Top: Biparentality proportion changing across brood sizes (posterior mean and 95% Cr.I. of the univariate Bayesian GLMM). Bottom: pairwise comparisons between brood size groups. Sample size per brood size group: $n_{\text{"3 or less"}} = 11$; $n_{\text{"4"}} = 26$; $n_{\text{"5"}} = 25$; $n_{\text{"6 or more"}} = 6$.

brood.size_pairwise	estimate	lower.HPD	upper.HPD
3 or less – 4	-0.475	-1.134	0.2066
3 or less – 5	-0.731	-1.391	-0.0336
3 or less - 6 or more	0.243	-0.721	1.2126
4 – 5	-0.256	-0.762	0.2836
4 - 6 or more	0.726	-0.118	1.6111
5 - 6 or more	0.976	0.141	1.8483
Point estimate displayed: median			
Results are given on the log odds ratio (not the response) scale.			
HPD interval probability: 0.95			

Table S2. Pairwise comparisons of biparentality differences between brood sizes.

Correlation between biparentality and relative parental provisioning (prey per chick)

Figure S3. Posterior distribution of correlation coefficients between biparentality proportion and prey per chick brought by the female partner at nightly scale ($\rho = 0.66$, 95%Cr.I. = [0.60, 0.72], iterations = 10,000).

Figure S4. Posterior distribution of correlation coefficients between biparentality proportion and prey per chick brought by the male partner at nightly scale ($\rho = -0.39$, 95%Cr.I. = $[-0.47, -0.29]$, iterations = 10,000).

Figure S5. Posterior distribution of correlation coefficients between biparentality proportion and prey per chick brought by the female partner at individual scale ($\rho = 0.77$, 95%Cr.I. = $[0.66, 0.85]$, iterations = 10,000).

Figure S6. Posterior distribution of correlation coefficients between biparentality proportion and prey per chick brought by the male partner at individual scale ($\rho = -0.45$, 95%Cr.I. = [-0.62, -0.25, iterations = 10,000]).

Tables of models displayed in Figure 2 (A, B, C, D)

All variables including “_z” or “.z” are continuous variables standardised as z-scores. Those variables including “M” or “F” refer to males and females, respectively, if the letter identifying the sex is missing it means that is relative to both parents combined. Specific variable abbreviations used in the tables:

- *prop.bip_z* → nightly biparentality proportion, as number of prey items brought to the nest by the female parent divided the total prey items brought by both parents.
- *vedba.avg.F_z* and *vedba.avg.M_z* → nightly mean VeDBA.
- *hunt.att.sum.F_z* and *hunt.att.sum.M_z* → nightly sum of hunting attempts.
- *prop.succ.dives.F_z* and *prop.succ.dives.F_z* → nightly hunting success, successful attempts divided nightly sum of hunting attempts.
- *prop.refuelF_z* and *prop.refuelM_z* → nightly self-feeding proportion, as prey items eaten divided the total prey captured.
- *area_wildflower.zsqrt* → Area of wildflower stripes (in km²) around a fixed buffer area around the nest box (1.5 km radius), sqrt-transformed.
- *YearF2020* → categorical variable “Year”. [2020] refers to the level of comparison in respect to the intercept level, Year [2019].

- *brood.size.change01F1* → Chick loss during the tagging period. [1] refers to the level of comparison in respect to the intercept level [0].

All tables show the median, mean and MAP estimate and its 95% Credible Intervals.

Parameter	Median	Mean	MAP	95% CrI
(Intercept)	-1.27	-1.27	-1.27	[-1.44, -1.10]
vedba.avg.F_z	0.24	0.24	0.24	[0.14, 0.35]
hunt.att.sum.F_z	0.40	0.40	0.40	[0.28, 0.51]
prop.refuelF_z	-0.41	-0.41	-0.41	[-0.54, -0.28]
prop.succ.dives.F_z	0.31	0.31	0.31	[0.21, 0.41]
vedba.avg.M_z	-0.12	-0.12	-0.12	[-0.22, -0.01]
hunt.att.sum.M_z	-0.31	-0.31	-0.31	[-0.43, -0.19]
prop.succ.dives.M_z	-0.26	-0.26	-0.26	[-0.36, -0.15]
prop.refuelM_z	0.07	0.07	0.07	[-0.02, 0.16]
area_wildflower.zsqrt	-0.11	-0.11	-0.11	[-0.22, 0.00]
yearF2020	0.06	0.06	0.06	[-0.18, 0.28]
brood.size.change01F1	0.02	0.02	0.03	[-0.20, 0.24]
Random effects SD/Cor: BroodID	0.29	0.29	0.30	[0.10, 0.43]

Table S3. Biparentality proportion as response variable

Parameter	Median	Mean	MAP	95% CrI
(Intercept)	2.82	2.82	2.82	[2.61, 3.03]
prop.bip_z	0.14	0.14	0.14	[0.02, 0.26]
vedba.avg.F_z	0.07	0.07	0.07	[-0.03, 0.17]
hunt.att.sum.F_z	0.25	0.25	0.24	[0.13, 0.36]
prop.refuelF_z	-0.09	-0.09	-0.09	[-0.20, 0.02]
prop.succ.dives.F_z	0.01	0.01	0.01	[-0.09, 0.10]
vedba.avg.M_z	0.16	0.16	0.16	[0.06, 0.26]
hunt.att.sum.M_z	0.75	0.75	0.75	[0.64, 0.86]
prop.succ.dives.M_z	0.44	0.44	0.44	[0.34, 0.54]
prop.refuelM_z	-0.07	-0.07	-0.07	[-0.15, 0.01]
area_wildflower.zsqrt	0.06	0.06	0.05	[-0.08, 0.20]
yearF2020	-0.15	-0.15	-0.14	[-0.44, 0.13]
brood.size.change[1]	-0.56	-0.56	-0.56	[-0.84, -0.29]
Random effects SD/Cor: BroodID	0.48	0.48	0.47	[0.35, 0.61]

Table S4. Prey per chick delivered by both parents as response variable

Parameter	Median	Mean	MAP	95% CrI
(Intercept)	0.77	0.77	0.76	[0.63, 0.91]
vedba.avg.M_z	0.02	0.02	0.02	[-0.04, 0.08]
hunt.att.sum.M_z	0.16	0.16	0.16	[0.10, 0.22]
prop.succ.dives.M_z	0.02	0.02	0.02	[-0.04, 0.08]
prop.refuelM_z	0.02	0.02	0.02	[-0.03, 0.07]
area_wildflower.zsqrt	-0.09	-0.09	-0.09	[-0.18, 0.00]
yearF2020	0.00	0.00	0.00	[-0.18, 0.18]
brood.size.change01F1	-0.23	-0.23	-0.23	[-0.40, -0.05]
Random effects SD/Cor: BroodID	0.29	0.29	0.28	[0.21, 0.38]

Table S5. Female prey per chick as response variable

Parameter	Median	Mean	MAP	95% CrI
(Intercept)	1.94	1.94	1.94	[1.67, 2.20]
vedba.avg.F_z	-0.02	-0.02	-0.02	[-0.13, 0.10]
hunt.att.sum.F_z	0.33	0.33	0.33	[0.21, 0.45]
prop.refuelF_z	0.02	0.02	0.01	[-0.11, 0.14]
prop.succ.dives.F_z	-0.04	-0.04	-0.04	[-0.14, 0.06]
area_wildflower.zsqrt	0.17	0.18	0.17	[0.00, 0.35]
yearF2020	0.08	0.08	0.08	[-0.28, 0.43]
brood.size.change01F1	-0.34	-0.34	-0.34	[-0.67, -0.01]
Random effects SD/Cor: BroodID	0.56	0.56	0.56	[0.35, 0.74]

Table S6. Male prey per chick as response variable

Tables of models displayed in Figure 3

All variables including “_z” or “.z” are continuous variables standardised as z-scores. Interactions between variables shown inserting “:” between the two specific variables in interaction. Specific variable abbreviations used in the tables:

- *prop.bip_z* → nightly biparentality proportion.
- *time.group2* and *time.group3* → chick measurement time, time.group1 to 3, respectively: before tagging, after tagging, before fledging. In the case of Model 3 and Model 4, only *time.group2* and *time.group3* are present since the response variable is the weight/wing measurement change between time1-time2 and time2-time3.
- *Rank2*, *Rank3* and *Rank4* → Chick rank: 1 = born first, 2 = second, 3 = third and 4 = born fourth or younger.

All tables show the median, mean and MAP estimate and its 95% Credible Intervals. Otherwise specified in the caption.

Model 1: chick’s absolute weight

Parameter	Median	Mean	MAP	95% CrI
(Intercept)	256.30	256.28	256.36	[246.81, 265.64]
prop.bip_z	5.79	5.78	5.67	[0.00, 11.50]
time.group2	74.76	74.78	74.66	[67.49, 82.09]
time.group3	109.68	109.71	109.76	[102.08, 117.43]
Rank2	-8.96	-8.97	-8.77	[-16.22, -1.85]
Rank3	-13.32	-13.31	-13.75	[-21.22, -5.52]
Rank4	-45.27	-45.30	-45.10	[-55.63, -35.11]

Table S7. Summary of posterior distribution (model without interactions)

Parameter	Median	Mean	MAP	95% CrI
(Intercept)	256.11	256.08	256.27	[246.57, 265.56]
prop.bip_z	5.72	5.68	5.75	[-7.65, 18.82]
time.group2	74.53	74.52	74.76	[67.21, 81.83]
time.group3	110.10	110.12	109.98	[102.35, 117.93]
Rank2	-9.01	-9.01	-8.85	[-16.26, -1.77]
Rank3	-12.41	-12.41	-12.72	[-20.47, -4.47]
Rank4	-46.45	-46.51	-46.40	[-57.13, -36.28]
prop.bip_z:time.group2	-1.17	-1.15	-1.10	[-15.65, 13.47]
prop.bip_z:time.group3	-3.35	-3.29	-3.69	[-17.72, 11.31]
prop.bip_z:Rank2	-0.11	-0.07	-0.30	[-15.71, 15.98]
prop.bip_z:Rank3	-0.57	-0.45	-0.93	[-17.64, 17.10]
prop.bip_z:Rank4	-1.03	-0.93	-1.71	[-19.11, 17.64]

prop.bip_z:time.group2:Rank2	5.47	5.45	5.58	[-14.17, 24.93]
prop.bip_z:time.group3:Rank2	5.28	5.23	5.46	[-13.50, 23.68]
prop.bip_z:time.group2:Rank3	-0.77	-0.80	-0.63	[-21.74, 20.23]
prop.bip_z:time.group3:Rank3	-5.49	-5.59	-5.70	[-26.02, 14.49]
prop.bip_z:time.group2:Rank4	11.57	11.53	12.10	[-9.71, 32.92]
prop.bip_z:time.group3:Rank4	10.08	9.97	10.58	[-12.15, 31.61]

Table S8. Summary of posterior distribution (model including interactions)

time.group	Rank	Fcoop trend	lower.HPD	upper.HPD
1	1	5.72	-7.834	18.6
2	1	4.54	-5.847	14.8
3	1	2.42	-6.701	11.3
1	2	5.65	-6.094	17.1
2	2	9.92	-0.226	20.0
3	2	7.60	-1.342	16.4
1	3	5.23	-7.652	18.6
2	3	3.27	-7.119	13.9
3	3	-3.66	-12.686	5.0
1	4	4.75	-9.012	18.4
2	4	15.15	4.347	26.4
3	4	11.44	2.288	20.7

Table S9. Summary of posterior slopes of third-way interaction. Point estimate displayed: median; HPD interval probability: 0.95; meaningful slopes in bold.

Model 2: chick's wing length

Parameter	Median	Mean	MAP	95% CrI
(Intercept)	109.78	109.76	110.14	[103.91, 115.54]
prop.bip_z	3.22	3.20	3.43	[-1.61, 7.98]
time.group2	56.43	56.42	56.45	[54.58, 58.29]
time.group3	164.61	164.61	164.59	[161.76, 167.42]
Rank2	-14.09	-14.09	-13.92	[-18.67, -9.47]
Rank3	-27.87	-27.86	-28.03	[-32.61, -23.16]
Rank4	-56.80	-56.79	-57.07	[-61.23, -52.34]

Table S10. Summary of posterior distribution (model without interactions)

Parameter	Median	Mean	MAP	95% CrI
(Intercept)	109.70	109.70	109.72	[103.96, 115.47]
prop.bip_z	2.64	2.62	2.77	[-3.50, 8.74]

time.group2	56.43	56.42	56.55	[54.58, 58.26]
time.group3	164.41	164.42	164.39	[161.57, 167.29]
Rank2	-13.89	-13.89	-14.00	[-18.54, -9.26]
Rank3	-27.80	-27.81	-27.66	[-32.39, -23.17]
Rank4	-57.33	-57.32	-57.49	[-61.75, -52.85]
prop.bip_z:time.group2	-2.71	-2.72	-2.55	[-6.98, 1.50]
prop.bip_z:time.group3	-3.72	-3.73	-3.93	[-10.62, 3.16]
prop.bip_z:Rank2	1.68	1.70	1.49	[-3.88, 7.31]
prop.bip_z:Rank3	-0.05	-0.05	0.17	[-5.78, 5.69]
prop.bip_z:Rank4	3.51	3.52	3.39	[-1.96, 9.06]
prop.bip_z:time.group2:Rank2	-0.18	-0.17	-0.34	[-5.81, 5.51]
prop.bip_z:time.group3:Rank2	5.49	5.49	5.57	[-3.43, 14.48]
prop.bip_z:time.group2:Rank3	0.45	0.44	0.39	[-5.33, 6.07]
prop.bip_z:time.group3:Rank3	3.17	3.15	3.80	[-5.71, 12.15]
prop.bip_z:time.group2:Rank4	3.14	3.13	3.11	[-2.30, 8.59]
prop.bip_z:time.group3:Rank4	5.81	5.84	5.18	[-2.69, 14.45]

Table S11. Summary of posterior distribution (model with interactions)

time.group	Rank	Fcoop trend	lower.HPD	upper.HPD
1	1	2.638	-3.523	8.70
2	1	-0.100	-6.041	5.85
3	1	-1.114	-8.960	7.15
1	2	4.319	-1.457	10.11
2	2	1.445	-4.394	7.22
3	2	6.082	-1.391	13.43
1	3	2.569	-3.429	8.57
2	3	0.296	-5.367	6.15
3	3	1.988	-5.187	9.26
1	4	6.169	0.260	11.64
2	4	6.566	0.909	12.01
3	4	8.259	1.632	15.12

Table S12. Summary of posterior slopes of third-way interaction. Point estimate displayed: median; HPD interval probability: 0.95; meaningful slopes in bold.

Model 3: chick's daily weight change

Parameter	Median	Mean	MAP	95% CI
(Intercept)	5.35	5.35	5.36	[4.51, 6.20]
prop.bip_z	0.76	0.76	0.73	[-0.57, 2.10]
time.group3	-5.93	-5.93	-5.96	[-6.67, -5.20]
Rank2	0.73	0.73	0.75	[-0.12, 1.58]

Rank3	1.51	1.51	1.57	[0.60, 2.41]
Rank4	2.94	2.94	2.93	[2.13, 3.73]

Table S13. Summary of posterior distribution (model without interactions)

Parameter	Median	Mean	MAP	95% CrI
sigma_Intercept	1.67	1.67	1.67	[1.55, 1.80]
(Intercept)	5.35	5.35	5.34	[4.51, 6.21]
prop.bip_z	0.77	0.77	0.77	[-0.60, 2.11]
time.group3	-5.93	-5.93	-5.91	[-6.67, -5.19]
Rank2	0.73	0.73	0.76	[-0.12, 1.57]
Rank3	1.50	1.51	1.48	[0.60, 2.41]
Rank4	2.94	2.94	2.93	[2.12, 3.75]
prop.bip_z:time.group3	-1.17	-1.17	-1.17	[-2.67, 0.33]
prop.bip_z:Rank2	-0.50	-0.50	-0.36	[-2.39, 1.40]
prop.bip_z:Rank3	-0.49	-0.49	-0.37	[-2.54, 1.59]
prop.bip_z:Rank4	0.05	0.05	0.02	[-1.76, 1.85]
prop.bip_z:time.group3:Rank2	1.04	1.05	1.03	[-1.11, 3.20]
prop.bip_z:time.group3:Rank3	0.30	0.30	0.26	[-2.03, 2.61]
prop.bip_z:time.group3:Rank4	-0.39	-0.39	-0.35	[-2.43, 1.63]

Table S14. Summary of posterior distribution (model with interactions)

time.group	Rank	Fcoop trend	lower.HPD	upper.HPD
2	1	0.770	-0.572	2.130
3	1	-0.402	-1.131	0.318
2	2	0.262	-1.140	1.646
3	2	0.142	-0.615	0.914
2	3	0.275	-1.314	1.889
3	3	-0.592	-1.399	0.239
2	4	0.818	-0.409	2.047
3	4	-0.748	-1.386	-0.106

Table S15. Summary of posterior slopes of third-way interaction Point estimate displayed: median; HPD interval probability: 0.95; meaningful slopes in bold.

Model 4: chick's daily wing length growth

Parameter	Median	Mean	MAP	95% CI
(Intercept)	5.06	5.06	5.06	[4.82, 5.30]

prop.bip_z	-0.16	-0.16	-0.17	[-0.53, 0.21]
time.group3	-1.33	-1.33	-1.33	[-1.49, -1.16]
Rank2	0.26	0.26	0.25	[-0.01, 0.53]
Rank3	0.51	0.51	0.52	[0.27, 0.76]
Rank4	0.65	0.65	0.65	[0.40, 0.90]

Table S16. Summary of posterior distribution (model without interactions)

Parameter	Median	Mean	MAP	95% CI
sigma_Intercept	0.40	0.40	0.40	[0.25, 0.55]
(Intercept)	5.06	5.06	5.05	[4.82, 5.30]
prop.bip_z	-0.16	-0.16	-0.16	[-0.53, 0.21]
time.group3	-1.33	-1.33	-1.32	[-1.49, -1.16]
Rank2	0.26	0.26	0.27	[-0.01, 0.53]
Rank3	0.51	0.51	0.53	[0.27, 0.76]
Rank4	0.65	0.65	0.65	[0.40, 0.90]
prop.bip_z:time.group3	0.02	0.02	0.04	[-0.42, 0.47]
prop.bip_z:Rank2	8.40e-03	9.53e-03	-2.70e-03	[-0.47, 0.48]
prop.bip_z:Rank3	0.15	0.15	0.17	[-0.28, 0.58]
prop.bip_z:Rank4	0.38	0.38	0.38	[-0.06, 0.81]
prop.bip_z:time.group3:Rank2	0.13	0.13	0.13	[-0.46, 0.71]
prop.bip_z:time.group3:Rank3	-0.08	-0.09	-0.09	[-0.61, 0.44]
prop.bip_z:time.group3:Rank4	-0.37	-0.37	-0.37	[-0.90, 0.16]

Table S17. Summary of posterior distribution (model with interactions)

time.group	Rank	prop.bip_z.trend	lower.HPD	upper.HPD
2	1	-0.15810	-0.5259	0.2109
3	1	-0.13367	-0.3999	0.1388
2	2	-0.14889	-0.4625	0.1718
3	2	0.00209	-0.2310	0.2343
2	3	-0.00560	-0.2479	0.2249
3	3	-0.06713	-0.2351	0.0994
2	4	0.22104	-0.0103	0.4532
3	4	-0.12406	-0.2952	0.0348

Table S18. Summary of posterior slopes of third-way interaction. Point estimate displayed: median; HPD interval probability: 0.95; meaningful slopes in bold.

Nestling success or survival at GPS recovery

All variables including “_z” or “.z” are continuous variables standardised as z-scores. Those variables including “M” or “F” refer to males and females, respectively, if the letter identifying the sex is missing it means that is relative to both parents combined. Specific variable abbreviations used in the tables:

- *prey.nest.Fcoop01_z* or *prop.bip_z* → mean pair biparentality proportion, as number of prey items brought to the nest by the female parent divided the total prey items brought by both parents.
- *prey.per.chick_z* → sum of prey items brought by both parents divided the number of nestlings
- *vedba.avg.F_z* and *vedba.avg.M_z* → mean VeDBA.
- *hunt.att.sum.F_z* and *hunt.att.sum.M_z* → sum of hunting attempts.
- *prop.succ.dives.F_z* and *prop.succ.dives.M_z* → hunting success, successful attempts divided nightly sum of hunting attempts.
- *prop.refuelF_z* and *prop.refuelM_z* → self-feeding proportion, as prey items eaten divided the total prey captured.
- *area_wildflower.zsqrt* → Area of wildflower stripes (in km²) around a fixed buffer area around the nest box (1.5 km radius), sqrt-transformed.
- *YearF2020* → categorical variable “Year”. [2020] refers to the level of comparison in respect to the intercept level, Year [2019].
- *brood.size.change01F1* → Chick loss during the tagging period. [1] refers to the level of comparison in respect to the intercept level [0].

All tables show the median, mean and MAP estimate and its 95% Credible Intervals.

Figure S7. Summary plot of the Bayesian Generalised mixed effect models showing the standardised effects of foraging performance and behaviours of parents, area of wildflower strips, year on nestling survival (nestlings survived divided total eggs laid). Standardised effects are expressed as posterior distributions with a mean (dot), and the 95% Credible Intervals limits (line). Different colours highlight different models (see Table S19).

	Parameter	Median	Mean	MAP	95% CrI
Model 1	(Intercept)	0.81	0.81	0.81	[0.50, 1.16]
	prop.bip_z	0.17	0.17	0.17	[-0.08, 0.44]
	prey.per.chick_z	0.17	0.17	0.16	[-0.08, 0.44]
	area_wildflower.zsqrt	0.07	0.08	0.08	[-0.20, 0.36]
	yearF2020	0.38	0.38	0.39	[-0.15, 0.92]
	Random effects SD/Cor: BroodID	0.39	0.39	0.45	[0.02, 0.85]
Model 2	(Intercept)	0.77	0.78	0.77	[0.47, 1.12]

	prop.bip_z	0.17	0.17	0.18	[-0.08, 0.43]
	area_wildflower.zsqrt	0.10	0.10	0.09	[-0.18, 0.38]
	yearF2020	0.43	0.43	0.42	[-0.09, 0.97]
	Random effects SD/Cor: BroodID	0.40	0.40	0.41	[0.03, 0.85]
Model 3					
	(Intercept)	0.79	0.80	0.79	[0.49, 1.14]
	prey.per.chick_z	0.18	0.18	0.18	[-0.08, 0.43]
	area_wildflower.zsqrt	0.03	0.03	0.05	[-0.23, 0.30]
	yearF2020	0.39	0.39	0.39	[-0.14, 0.92]
	Random effects SD/Cor: BroodID	0.37	0.38	0.40	[0.02, 0.84]
Model 4					
	(Intercept)	0.81	0.81	0.81	[0.50, 1.16]
	prey.per.chickM_z	0.04	0.04	0.05	[-0.22, 0.31]
	prey.per.chickF_z	0.26	0.26	0.25	[0.01, 0.52]
	area_wildflower.zsqrt	0.09	0.09	0.09	[-0.18, 0.38]
	yearF2020	0.38	0.38	0.37	[-0.15, 0.92]
	Random effects SD/Cor: BroodID	0.38	0.39	0.39	[0.02, 0.84]
Model 5					
	(Intercept)	0.87	0.88	0.87	[0.56, 1.23]
	hunt.att.sum.M_z	0.32	0.32	0.31	[0.04, 0.61]
	hunt.att.sum.F_z	8.22e-03	8.42e-03	0.02	[-0.24, 0.26]
	area_wildflower.zsqrt	-5.78e-04	9.93e-05	-7.98e-03	[-0.27, 0.27]
	yearF2020	0.21	0.21	0.21	[-0.33, 0.76]
	Random effects SD/Cor: BroodID	0.35	0.36	0.32	[0.02, 0.82]
Model 6					
	(Intercept)	0.82	0.83	0.83	[0.52, 1.17]
	prop.succ.dives.F_z	0.23	0.23	0.23	[-0.02, 0.50]
	prop.succ.dives.M_z	-0.24	-0.24	-0.25	[-0.49, -0.01]
	area_wildflower.zsqrt	0.05	0.06	0.05	[-0.21, 0.33]
	yearF2020	0.36	0.36	0.34	[-0.17, 0.89]
	Random effects SD/Cor: BroodID	0.34	0.36	0.37	[0.02, 0.81]
Model 7					
	(Intercept)	0.84	0.85	0.83	[0.54, 1.19]
	vedba.avg.F_z	0.25	0.25	0.26	[0.02, 0.49]
	vedba.avg.M_z	0.20	0.20	0.21	[-0.04, 0.44]
	area_wildflower.zsqrt	0.06	0.06	0.06	[-0.19, 0.33]
	yearF2020	0.29	0.29	0.30	[-0.22, 0.81]
	Random effects SD/Cor: BroodID	0.31	0.33	0.32	[0.02, 0.77]

Table S19. Summary of models predicting nestling survival. Posterior distribution mean and 95% credible intervals are shown.